

Analysis of the Effect of Good Corporate Governance Implementation on Banking Financial Performance Measured Through the ROA & ROE Ratio in Sharia Commercial Banks in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

The implementation of Good Corporate Governance for Islamic banking is regulated in PBI No. 11/33 / PBI / 2009 concerning the Implementation of Good Corporate Governance for Islamic Commercial Banks and Sharia Business Units. This study will show whether there is a relationship or influence from the implementation of GCG through several indicators such as the number of boards of directors, the board of commissioners, the number of meetings on the sharia supervisory board, and also the number of meetings of the audit committee at each Islamic commercial bank in Indonesia, with the dependent variable, namely financial performance as measured by Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE). The number of research samples is from 10 Islamic commercial banks listed on the IDX for the period 2018-2019 with a purposive sampling technique. This study uses secondary data from annual reports and GCG implementation reports from each Islamic commercial bank. The analytical method used in this research is through hypothesis testing with regression analysis using the IBM SPSS V21. The test results found that simultaneously through the simultaneous F test, GCG has a positive effect on Return on Assets, and GCG simultaneously has no effect on Return on Equity.

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of the capital market in Indonesia is currently growing rapidly, which causes many companies to be required to immediately improve their performance so that they can compete with other companies (Novitasari et al. 2019). The Islamic capital market is all activities in the capital market based on Islamic principles (As sajjad et al. 2021). Indonesia, with the majority of its population being Muslim, is one of the countries that has the largest share of the Islamic capital market in the world (Fadhillah 2018). It is proven that

nowadays there are more and more companies, especially Islamic banking, which are registering their companies (listing) on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (Tandean and Winnie 2016). By registering Islamic banking on the stock market, the company is also obliged to report all activities in the company either through financial reports (quarterly reports, quarterly reports, annual reports) or through non-financial reports (Surepno and Minoto 2018).

Information in financial reports is one of the important information for stakeholders to assess the performance of a company and help them in the process of making the right decision (Hartutik

and Asmita 2016). The pros and cons of decisions taken will depend and be determined by the quality of information generated from financial reports (Vivi Adeyani 2016). Islamic banking requires high trust from its customers, because without the trust of customers or stakeholders, Islamic banking will find it difficult to carry out their business continuity (Kusumaningrostaty and Mutasowifin 2014). In addition, trust from customers can support the welfare of stakeholders and will increase company value (Tandean and Winnie 2016).

One of the ways to increase company value is through reporting and implementing Good Corporate Governance (Sulistiyo et al. 2020). The implementation of Good Corporate Governance for Islamic banking is regulated in PBI No. 11/33/PBI/2009 concerning the Implementation of Good Corporate Governance for Islamic Commercial Banks and Sharia Business Units (Prasojo 2015). The implementation of Good Corporate Governance is very necessary in order to build trust from the public and other stakeholders (Wijaya et al. 2021). In addition to the implementation of Good Corporate Governance, to increase corporate value can be built through financial performance (Hisamuddin and others 2012). Financial performance is a description of the conditions or economic results achieved by Islamic banking at a certain time (Kuncorowati et al. 2021). One of the parameters of the financial statements used to measure the performance of company management is earnings (Kusumaningrostaty and Mutasowifin 2014). Earnings information aims to assess management performance, help estimate long-term profitability, and estimate investment risks (Kusumaningrostaty and Mutasowifin 2014).

In this study, the authors will show whether there is a relationship or influence from the implementation of Good Corporate Governance in Islamic Commercial Banks on banking financial performance, through the company's profitability ratio as measured by Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) in Islamic Commercial Banks in Indonesia (Roos Ana et al. 2021).

Research Problem

1. Is there any influence from the implementation of Good Corporate Governance in Islamic commercial banks on Return on Assets?
2. Is there any influence from the implementation of Good Corporate

Governance in Islamic commercial banks on Return on Equity?

The Objectives of the Research

1. To test and prove empirically the effect of the implementation of Good Corporate Governance in Islamic commercial banks on banking financial performance through Return on Assets in the 2018-2019 period
2. To test and prove the effect of the implementation of Good Corporate Governance in Islamic commercial banks on banking financial performance through Return on Equity for the period 2018-2019.

Research Benefits

1. Theoretical Benefits

Theoretically, it is hoped that the results of this study will provide an understanding and reference regarding the analysis of the effect of the implementation of Good Corporate Governance in Islamic commercial banks on banking financial performance through Return on Assets and Return on Equity.

2. Practical Benefits

In practical terms, this research is expected to be able to provide understanding to Islamic banking, especially regarding the analysis of the effect of the application of Good Corporate Governance in Islamic commercial banks on banking financial performance through Return on Assets and Return on Equity.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESES

Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholders are parties or groups of stakeholders, either directly or indirectly, to the activities or activities of a company (Aduroh and Paramu 2021). Stakeholder theory means that a company is not an entity that only operates for its own interests but must provide benefits for its stakeholders (Fadhillah 2018). The existence of a company is strongly influenced by the support provided by stakeholders to the company (Liyundira et al. 2021). Therefore, company management is required to report company information both through financial and non-financial reports to stakeholders without reducing the level of credibility (Sri Kustono and Adi Nanggala 2019).

Islamic Banking

Law No. 21 of 2008 concerning Sharia Banking, explains that Islamic banking is everything that concerns Sharia Banks and Sharia

Business Units, including institutions, business activities, and methods and processes in carrying out their business activities (Irmadariyani et al. 2019). Sharia Banks are banks that carry out their business activities based on Sharia Principles and by type consist of Sharia Commercial Banks and Sharia Rural Banks (Purnamawati et al. 2019). The functions of Islamic commercial banks and Islamic business units are in accordance with Law No. 21 of 2008, which is obliged to carry out functions in collecting and distributing funds from the community, as well as carrying out social functions in the community (Djaya Atmadja et al. 2019).

Profitability in Financial Statements (*Return on Assets*)

Profitability is the ability of a company to earn profits in a certain period and as a measure of the effectiveness of a company's management (Kusumaningrostaty and Mutasowifin 2014). The greater the level of company profitability indicates that the company is able to get greater profits (Siswanti 2016). In this study, the authors used the Return on Assets (ROA) analysis as a measure of company profitability (Irmadariyani 2019). ROA is an indicator of a bank's ability to generate returns on a number of assets owned by the bank (Nisa, N W; Paramu 2019). The greater the Return on Assets (ROA) of a bank, the greater the level of profit achieved by the bank, and the better the position of the bank in terms of asset use (Surepno and Minoto 2018).

In Bank Indonesia Circular Letter No. 9 of 2007 states that Return on Assets is a supporting ratio in calculating profitability for Islamic banks (Ariful Habib et al. 2020). This ratio is used to measure the success of management in generating profits (Sumani and Roziq 2020).

Return on Equity

The ROE value can be calculated by comparing the amount of profit after tax with the core capital of Islamic banks (Kustono 2021). The higher this ratio, the better the bank's ability to earn profits.

Good Corporate Governance

Good Corporate Governance (GCG) is basically a system that regulates, manages and oversees the business management process to smooth relationships between management, shareholders and other interested parties with the aim of creating added value for the company

(Eriandani and Winarno 2021). GCG arises because there is a separation between ownership and control of the company, or often known as agency problems. Corporate governance is needed to reduce agency problems between owners and managers (Park 2017). As according to Bank Indonesia in PBI number 11/33/PBI/2009, GCG, hereinafter referred to as GCG, is a governance of banks to apply principles such as the principle of transparency, accountability, responsibility, professional and fairness (Fadhillah 2018). So it can be concluded from several expert opinions above, Good Corporate Governance is a corporate governance system within the framework of corporate control and aims to create added value for the company (Agustin et al. 2021).

Previous Research

Research conducted by Prasojo (2015) proves that the implementation of GCG can increase the ROA of Islamic banks. However, research conducted by Hartutik and Asmita (2016), Purwanto (2014) and Siswanti (2016) proved the opposite result, namely that there was no significant effect between the implementation of GCG and ROA. Research conducted (Prasojo 2015); and (Hartutik and Asmita 2016) prove that the implementation of good corporate governance can increase the ROE of Islamic banks. According to Hisamuddin and others (2012), there is a positive influence between GCG on the financial performance of Islamic commercial banks with the financial performance indicators used in the form of ROA and ROE (Fadhillah 2018).

Research Framework

Formulation Research Hypothesis

1. Good corporate governance on Return On Assets

H1 : There is an effect of the implementation of Good Corporate Governance on banking financial performance (ROA).

- a) Board of Directors
H1(a) : GCG (Board of Directors) affects the company's financial performance (ROA)
- b) Board of Commissioners
H1(b) : GCG (Board of Commissioners) affects the company's financial performance (ROA).
- c) Sharia Supervisory Board Meeting
H1(c) : GCG (SSB Meeting) affects the company's financial performance (ROA).
- d) Audit Committee Meeting
H1(d) : GCG (Audit Committee Meeting) affects the company's financial performance (ROA).

2. Good corporate governance on Return On Equity

H2 : There is an effect of the implementation of Good Corporate Governance on banking financial performance (ROE).

- a) Board of Directors
H2(a) : GCG (Board of Directors) affects the company's financial performance (ROE)
- b) Board of Commissioners
H2(b) : GCG (Board of Commissioners) affects the company's financial performance (ROE).
- c) Sharia Supervisory Board Meeting
H2(c) : GCG (SSB Meeting) affects the company's financial performance (ROE).
- d) Audit Committee Meeting
H2(d) : GCG (Audit Committee Meeting) affects the company's financial performance (ROE).

3. RESEARCH METHOD

Research object

The object of research used in this study is an Islamic commercial bank that has been listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange from 2018 to 2019 time period.

Type of research

This research, when viewed from the method, belongs to the type of research that is associative in nature, namely the existence of a relationship or influence of one variable with another. In Sugiyono (2010:36) what is meant by associative is that there is a relationship between

two or more variables. This research is included in the type of associative explanatory research, where the relationship between these variables is formulated in the research hypothesis that will be tested for truth.

Population and Sample

The population used in this study are Islamic commercial banks that have been listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. The sample size used is 10 Islamic commercial banks listed on the IDX for the period 2018-2019, including:

- 1) Bank BCA Syariah
- 2) Bank BNI Syariah
- 3) Bank BRI Syariah
- 4) Maybank Syariah
- 5) Bank Muamalat Indonesia
- 6) Bank Mega Syariah
- 7) Bank Mandiri Syariah
- 8) Bank Bukopin Syariah
- 9) Panin Dubai Sharia Bank
- 10) Bank BTPN Syariah

The sampling technique is purposive sampling, the sample selection techniques that have specific goals or targets in choosing the sample is not random sample. The criteria are as follows:

- a) Sharia commercial banks that have gone public and have been listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange for the 2018-2019 period
- b) Islamic commercial banks that publish complete annual reports and reports on the implementation of GCG on the IDX in the 2018-2019 period
- c) Have complete data related to the variables used in the study.

Types and Sources of Data

The type of data used in this research is documentary data. Documentary data is data that contains what and when an event or transaction, as well as who is involved in an incident. Sources of data in this research is using secondary data, which is a source of research data obtained by researchers indirectly through an intermediary medium (obtained and recorded others) for instance, evidence, records or historical reports that have been compiled in an archive (documentary data) published and not published. Secondary data in this study were obtained through financial reports from Islamic commercial banks, annual reports and good

corporate governance (GCG) reports for Islamic commercial banks for the period 2018-2019.

Data collection technique

The data collection method used in this research is through the documentation method, namely the data collection method by studying notes or documents. In this case, the note in question is the company's annual report and reports on the implementation of GCG in every Islamic commercial bank in Indonesia. The technique of collecting data through documentation techniques is carried out by finding and collecting references through scientific journals, scientific articles, and other secondary data.

Operational Definition of Variables

The independent variable is a type of variable that explains or affects other variables. The independent variable in this study is good corporate governance as measured by the indicators of the board of directors, board of commissioners, sharia supervisory board, and audit committee.

The dependent variable is a type of variable that is described or influenced by the independent variable. The dependent variable in this study is the financial performance of banks through ROA and ROE indicators in Islamic commercial banks in Indonesia.

Independent Variables:

a. X1 (Board of Directors)

The Board of Directors is a corporate organ that is authorized and fully responsible for the management of the company for the benefit of the company in accordance with the aims and objectives of the company and represents the company, both inside and outside the court in accordance with the provisions of the articles of association as referred to in Law Number 40 of 2007 concerning Limited Companies

b. X2 (Board of Commissioners)

The Board of Commissioners is a corporate organ that is tasked with conducting general and/or specific supervision in accordance with the articles of association and providing advice to the Board of Directors as referred to in Law Number 40 of 2007 concerning Limited Companies.

c. X3 (Number of BBS Meeting)

One of the derivatives of implementing sharia compliance, namely the existence of the

Sharia Supervisory Board (Surepno and Minoto 2018). Sharia Supervisory Board is a board assigned to provide advice and suggestions to the Board of Directors as well as supervise Bank activities to comply with Sharia Principles

d. X4 (Audit Committee Meeting)

The Audit Committee as referred to in Paragraph 87 paragraph (1) letter c has the duties and responsibilities of at least, namely evaluating the implementation of internal audits in order to assess the adequacy of internal control including the adequacy of the financial reporting process and coordinating with the Public Accountant Office for the effectiveness of implementation of external audit

Dependent Variables:

a. Y1 (ROA)

ROA as a measure of profitability financial performance shows the company's management's ability to generate income from managing assets to generate profits.

b. Y2 (ROE)

ROE is calculated by comparing the amount of after-tax profits with core capital of Islamic banks.

Data Analysis Techniques

The analysis method used in this research is through hypothesis testing with regression analysis using the IBM SPSS V21 tool and using the annual financial reports disclosed by Islamic commercial banks in Indonesia through data from IDX Syariah. Before testing the hypothesis, first the classical assumption test is carried out. The classical assumption test consists of normality test, multicollinearity test, autocorrelation test, and heteroscedasticity test (Adita et al. 2021).

The normality test is used to see whether the dependent variable and independent variable regression models have spread or the data has been normally distributed or not, through the Kolmogorov Smirnov (K-S test), with a significance level of > 0.05 . The multicollinearity test is carried out to avoid habits in the decision-making process regarding the effect of the partial test of each independent variable on the dependent variable. The autocorrelation test can be done by detecting the presence or absence of autocorrelation through the Durbin Watson test (DW Test).

Then after testing the classical assumptions, the next step is to test the hypothesis using Linear Regression with the F test and the t

test. The F test is carried out by looking at the significance value of the F and F table in the regression output using SPSS with a significant 0.05 ($\alpha = 5\%$). While in the t test, namely through the significance value of t and the comparison of t count with t table. If the research results show t count < t table at a significant rate of 0.05 then Ho is accepted and Ha is rejected, whereas if the research results show t count > t table at a significant rate of 0.05 then Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted (Riduwan: 2010).

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION
Description of Research Results

Based on data obtained from the annual reports of each Islamic commercial bank and reports on the implementation of GCG in the 2018-2019 period obtained through the respective bank websites, the authors obtained the following research data:

NAMA BANK	DEWAN DIREKSI	DEWAN KOMISARIS	JUMLAH RAPAT DPS	RAPAT KOMITE AUDIT	ROA	ROE
2018						
BCA SYARIAH	3	4	12	8	1,20	5,00
BNI SYARIAH	4	3	21	15	1,42	10,53
BRI SYARIAH	5	4	16	18	0,43	2,49
MAYBANK SYARIAH	8	6	18	20	1,74	10,71
MUAMALAT INDONESIA	5	3	13	11	0,08	1,17
MEGA SYARIAH	4	3	10	7	0,93	4,08
MANDIRI SYARIAH	6	5	12	13	0,88	8,21
BUKOPIN SYARIAH	4	4	14	12	0,02	0,26
PANIN DUBAI SYARIAH	4	3	12	12	0,26	1,45
BTPN SYARIAH	4	5	13	14	12,4	30,8
2019						
BCA SYARIAH	3	4	12	8	1,20	4,00
BNI SYARIAH	4	3	22	15	1,82	13,54
BRI SYARIAH	5	4	16	18	0,31	1,57
MAYBANK SYARIAH	8	6	18	20	1,45	7,73
MUAMALAT INDONESIA	5	3	13	11	0,05	0,45
MEGA SYARIAH	4	3	10	7	0,89	4,27
MANDIRI SYARIAH	6	5	12	13	1,69	15,66
BUKOPIN SYARIAH	4	4	14	12	0,04	0,23
PANIN DUBAI SYARIAH	4	3	12	12	0,25	1,08
BTPN SYARIAH	4	5	12	14	13,6	31,2

Source: annual reports and GCG implementation reports for the period 2018-2019 on the websites of each Islamic commercial bank (processed)

Hypothesis Test

1. The First Hypothesis (GCG Effect On ROA)

a) Classic Assumption Test

- Auto Correlation Test (Durbin Watson)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	,690 ^a	,476	,336	3,10143	2,117

a. Predictors: (Constant), Jumlah_Rapat_Komite_Audit, Jumlah_Dewan_Komisaris, Jumlah_Dewan_Direksi, Jumlah_Rapat_DPS
b. Dependent Variable: ROA

In this autocorrelation test is tested with the value of Durbin Watson on model output table

summary. The value indicator when there are no autocorrelation symptoms is if the Durbin Watson value is between du to 4-du. In the table above the Durbin Watson value is 2.117. While the value of du can be seen in Durbin Watson's table with a significance of 0.05 (k = 4, n = 20), it was found that the value of du = 1.8283 and 4-du = 2.18. So it can be concluded that there is no autocorrelation symptom in this research data because the Durbin Watson value lies between du to 4-du.

- Multicollinearity Test

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	,464	4,433		,105	,918		
	Jumlah_Dewan_Direksi	-2,401	,821	-,871	-2,923	,011	,394	2,539
	Jumlah_Dewan_Komisaris	2,659	1,046	,717	2,543	,023	,440	2,274
	Jumlah_Rapat_DPS	-,297	,353	-,263	-,840	,414	,358	2,797
	Jumlah_Rapat_Komite_Audit	,492	,407	,507	1,209	,245	,199	5,030

a. Dependent Variable: ROA

Multicollinearity test was performed using the Tolerance and VIF methods. The values that are used as benchmarks in decision making are the Tolerance and VIF values. A good Tolerance value when it has a value greater than 0.100 (Tolerance > 0.100) and has a VIF value less than 10.00; VIF < 10.00 (Imam Ghozali 2011: 107-108). This condition illustrates that the data does not occur multicollinearity symptoms.

Based on the data above, the tolerance value for each independent variable is greater than 0.100 and the VIF value on each independent variable is less than 10.00. Therefore, it can be concluded that there are no symptoms of multicollinearity.

- Normality Test - One sample kolmogrof

NPar Tests

	Unstandardized Residual
N	20
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	
Mean	,0000000
Std. Deviation	2,75569341
Most Extreme Differences	
Absolute	,143
Positive	,143
Negative	-,120
Test Statistic	,143
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	,200 ^{c,d}

a. Test distribution is Normal.
b. Calculated from data.
c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.
d. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

In this Kolmogorof test, it was found that the Sig value was above 0.05, namely 0.200 so that the data were normally distributed.

b) Hypothesis Test with Partial t Test (Multiple Linear Regression)

Basis for decision making partial t test may be through the significant value and comparative value of t arithmetic with t table. The following can be seen in the output coefficient table.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	.464	4,433		,105	,918		
	Jumlah_Dewan_Direksi	-2,401	,821	-,871	-2,923	,011	,394	2,539
	Jumlah_Dewan_Komisaris	2,659	1,046	,717	2,543	,023	,440	2,274
	Jumlah_Rapat_DPS	-,297	,353	-,263	-,840	,414	,358	2,797
	Jumlah_Rapat_Komite_Audit	,492	,407	,507	1,209	,245	,199	5,030

a. Dependent Variable: ROA

- Based on the significance value, the output table above shows that the significance value on the number of boards of directors and boards of commissioners is less than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the hypothesis is accepted, that is, there is an influence between the number of boards of directors and commissioners on ROA. While the significance value on the variable number of SSB and audit committee meetings was found to be Sig more than 0.05, which means the hypothesis is rejected, namely the number of SSB and audit committee meetings has no effect on ROA.
- Based on the comparison between the t value and the t table, the basis for the decision is if the t value > t table then the hypothesis is accepted, whereas if the t value < t table, then the hypothesis is rejected. The t value can be seen in the output table above, while the t table value is obtained through the t table which shows that the t table value (0.025; 15) is 2.131.

In the output table above, it is found that the t value in the variable number of commissioners is more than t table, which is 2.543 so that the hypothesis is accepted, which means that the number of commissioners has an effect on ROA. As for the other variables, the t value is smaller than the t table, which means that the hypothesis is rejected

c) Hypothesis Test with Simultaneous F Test

This simultaneous F test can be done through the significance value and the comparison of the calculated F value with the F table. The following can be seen in the ANOVA output table

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	130,824	4	32,706	3,400	,036 ^b
	Residual	144,283	15	9,619		
	Total	275,107	19			

a. Dependent Variable: ROA

b. Predictors: (Constant), Jumlah_Rapat_Komite_Audit, Jumlah_Dewan_Komisaris, Jumlah_Dewan_Direksi, Jumlah_Rapat_DPS

- Based on the significance value, it was found that GCG simultaneously affects ROA (Sig < 0.05)
- Based on the comparison of the calculated F value with the F table it was found that the calculated F value > F table, namely 3.4 > 3.01. This means that GCG (X) simultaneously affects ROA (Y1).

2. The Second Hypothesis (GCG Effect On ROE)

a) Classic Assumption Test

- Multicollinearity Test

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-,9265	11,402		-,813	,429		
	Jumlah_Dewan_Direksi	-,4172	2,113	-,627	-1,975	,067	,394	2,539
	Jumlah_Dewan_Komisaris	7,226	2,690	,808	2,688	,017	,440	2,274
	Jumlah_Rapat_DPS	,233	,908	,086	,257	,801	,358	2,797
	Jumlah_Rapat_Komite_Audit	,338	1,047	,145	,323	,751	,199	5,030

a. Dependent Variable: ROE

Based on the output data above, the tolerance value on each independent variable is greater than 0.100 and the VIF value on each independent variable is less than 10.00. Therefore, it can be concluded that there are no symptoms of multicollinearity.

• Normality Test - one sample kolmogrof

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		20
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	,0000000
	Std. Deviation	7,08854377
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	,106
	Positive	,106
	Negative	-,078
Test Statistic		,106
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		,200 ^{c,d}

In this Kolmogorof test, it was found that the Sig value was above 0.05, namely 0.200 so that the data were normally distributed.

b) Hypothesis Test with Partial t Test

Basis for decision making partial t test may be through the significant value and comparative value of t arithmetic with t table. The following can be seen in the output coefficient table.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-9,265	11,402		-,813	,429		
	Jumlah_Dewan_Direksi	-4,172	2,113	-,627	-1,975	,067	,394	2,539
	Jumlah_Dewan_Komisaris	7,226	2,690	,808	2,686	,017	,440	2,274
	Jumlah_Rapat_DPS	,233	,908	,086	,257	,801	,358	2,797
	Jumlah_Rapat_Komite_Audit	,338	1,047	,145	,323	,751	,199	5,030

a. Dependent Variable: ROE

- Based on the significance value, it is known that the significance value on the number of commissioners is less than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the hypothesis is accepted, that is, there is an influence between the number of boards of commissioners on ROA. Meanwhile, the significance value of the variable number of directors, number of SSB meetings and audit committee was found to be Sig more than 0.05, which means that the hypothesis is rejected, namely the number of directors, the number of SSB meetings and the audit committee have no effect on ROA.
- Based on the comparison between the t value and the t table, the basis for the decision is if the t value > t table then the hypothesis is accepted, whereas if the t value < t table, then the hypothesis is rejected. The t value can be seen in the output table above, while the t table value is obtained through the t table which shows that the t table value (0.025; 15) is 2.131. In the output table above, it is found that the t value in the variable number of

commissioners is more than t table, which is equal to 2.686, so the hypothesis is accepted, which means that the number of commissioners has an effect on ROA. As for the other variables, the t value is smaller than the t table, which means that the hypothesis is rejected.

c) Hypothesis Test with Simultaneous f Test

This simultaneous F test can be done through the significance value and the comparison of the calculated F value with the F table. The following can be seen in the ANOVA output table.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	645,761	4	161,440	2,537	,084 ^b
	Residual	954,702	15	63,647		
	Total	1600,463	19			

a. Dependent Variable: ROE

b. Predictors: (Constant), Jumlah_Rapat_Komite_Audit, Jumlah_Dewan_Komisaris, Jumlah_Dewan_Direksi, Jumlah_Rapat_DPS

- Based on the significance value, it was found that simultaneous GCG had no effect on ROA (Sig > 0.05).
- Based on the comparison of the calculated F value with the F table it was found that the calculated F value < F table, namely 2.537 < 3.01. This means that simultaneous GCG (X) has no effect on ROA (Y1).

The Results

Based on these results, we can conclude that:

1. The first hypothesis (GCG Effect on ROA)

- H1 (a): The number of boards of directors has a partial effect on Return on Assets.
- H1 (b): The number of commissioners has a partial effect on Return on Assets.
- H1 (c): The number of Sharia Supervisory Board meetings partially has no effect on Return on Assets.
- H1 (d): The number of audit committee meetings partially has no effect on Return on Assets.

Meanwhile, through simultaneous F Test, Good Corporate Governance has an effect on Return on Assets.

2. The second hypothesis (GCG Effect on ROE)

- H2 (a): The number of the board of directors has no partial effect on Return on Equity.
- H2 (b): The number of commissioners of directors has a partial effect on Return on Equity.
- H2 (c): The number of Sharia Supervisory Board meetings partially has no effect on Return on Equity.
- H2 (d): The number of audit committee meetings partially has no effect on Return on Equity.

Meanwhile, through simultaneous F Test, Good Corporate Governance has no effect on Return on Equity.

5. CONCLUSION, IMPLICATION, SUGGESTION, AND LIMITATIONS

In this study, the authors show the relationship or influence of the implementation of Good Corporate Governance in Islamic Commercial Banks on banking financial performance through the company's profitability ratio as measured by return on assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) in Islamic Commercial Banks in Indonesia through several Classic assumption test and hypothesis test using SPSS. In testing it was found that simultaneously through the simultaneous F test, Good Corporate Governance has a positive effect on Return on Assets, and Good Corporate Governance simultaneously has no effect on Return on Equity.

Research Suggestions and Limitations

Limitations in this research that the authors simply take the object of research of Islamic commercial bank in Indonesia, which is actually true Islamic banking sector includes two components, namely the Islamic banks and Islamic business units.

Suggestions for further research, it is hoped that further researchers can consider using the object of research on all components of Islamic banking, namely Islamic commercial banks and Islamic business units, so that the research can show better overall results.

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